

DYNAMIC RESPONSE AND BUCKLING OF IMPERFECT LAMINATED THIN SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

The emphasis of this paper is to use a thin shell finite element to study the dynamic response and buckling behavior of a class of thin shell problems due to the effects of three parameters with design significance: (1) axisymmetric and asymmetric imperfections; (2) orthotropic and anisotropic material properties; and (3) Rayleigh viscous damping. The results quantify the effect of amplitude of imperfections, which can significantly reduce the dynamic buckling load. The results also quantify the effects of orthotropic material parameter and viscous damping.

INTRODUCTION

In this study, a 48 d.o.f. doubly-curved quadrilateral imperfect laminated thin shell finite element is used. The formulation is based on the Kirchhoff-Love thin shell theory and the classical lamination theory. The geometric imperfections are treated by including additional terms in the strain-displacement equations. These imperfections are with reference to the overall shell geometry but not any specific laminate. The effect of viscous damping is considered using Rayleigh damping concept. The nonlinear equations of motion are written in the Lagrangian system and are solved by using an incremental algorithm based on Newmark's generalized operator.

Four types of thin shells are considered: (1) a laminated square plate; (2) an orthotropic annular spherical cap; (3) an orthotropic, axisymmetrically imperfect, whole spherical shell; and (4) an orthotropic, asymmetrically imperfect, spherical cap. While some basic results are compared with available solutions, extensive new results are also obtained to quantify the effect of the various parameters.

FORMULATION

A brief summary of the salient features of the element formulation is given below. The other details of the element derivation can be found in Réf. 1.

Strain-Displacement Relations

The strain-displacement relations for imperfect shells are represented in terms of Cartesian components and are an extended version of the strain-displacement relations given in tensor form by Niordson [2]. The effects of imperfections are included by modifying the tangential strain-displacement relations. These are given as

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} (f_{,\alpha}^i u_{i,\beta}^i + f_{i,\beta}^i u_{i,\alpha}^i + u_{,\alpha}^i u_{i,\beta}^i + u_{,\alpha}^i v_{i,\beta}^i + u_{i,\beta}^i v_{i,\alpha}^i) \quad (1)$$

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where f^i , u^i , and v^i are the Cartesian components of the middle surface, displacement, and imperfection at a given point on the shell surface, respectively; i varies from 1 to 3 and α and β from 1 to 2. In this study, the effects of imperfections on the curvature-displacement relations are ignored.

Laminate Constitutive Relations

The laminated anisotropic construction of the shell is assumed to be made up of n layers. Each lamina is assumed to be orthotropic with its principal material axes at an angle with the local coordinate axes. The stress-strain relation for each layer is expressed with reference to the local coordinate system through coordinate transformation. The stress and moment resultants are then related to the middle surface strains ϵ and the changes of curvature κ as [3]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $[\mathbf{N}]$ is the vector of resultant tangential stresses, $[\mathbf{M}]$ is the vector of resultant moments, and the coefficients of submatrix $[\mathbf{A}]$, $[\mathbf{B}]$ and $[\mathbf{D}]$ are given as

$$[\mathbf{A}_{ij}, \mathbf{B}_{ij}, \mathbf{D}_{ij}] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \mathbf{Q}_{ij} (1, z, z^2) dz \quad (i, j=1, 2, 3) \quad (3)$$

with \mathbf{Q}_{ij} denoting the plane-stress stiffness for individual layer and h the total shell thickness.

Damping Effect

To consider the effect of damping on the dynamic characteristics of buckling, the simple assumption of Rayleigh viscous damping [4] is used. The explicit viscous damping matrix is based on the proportional sum of the consistent mass and stiffness matrices as

$$[\mathbf{C}] = a [\mathbf{M}] + b [\mathbf{K}] \quad (4)$$

Two fundamental frequencies (ω_1 and ω_2) are used to obtain the two proportionality factors a and b :

$$2\xi_i \omega_i = a + b\omega_i^2 \quad i = 1 \text{ and } 2 \quad (5)$$

where ξ_1 and ξ_2 are the modal damping ratios corresponding to the first two modes, respectively.

The values of structural damping are rather difficult to quantify or even to estimate. However, modal damping ratios may be estimated on the basis of past experiments. The values for the modal damping ratios in structures are generally in the range of 2% to 10% [5]. In this study, the modal damping ratios ξ_1 and ξ_2 were both assumed as 5%.

RESULTS

Four types of thin shells were considered. All loadings were considered as uniform pressure. For the dynamic analysis, the pressure was assumed to be a step function with infinite duration. In all the examples studied, a sufficiently fine Gauss grid (5x5) was used to perform numerical integration to obtain the element stiffness and mass matrices. All calculations were performed using a CYBER 205 vectorized supercomputer at Purdue University.

(1) Dynamic Response of a Laminated Square Plate under Uniform Step Pressure

Dynamic response of a 10-ply $([0^0/90^0/0^0/90^0/0^0]_s)$ Graphite/Epoxy laminated square plate, as shown in Fig. 1, under uniform step pressure were performed. The square plate was assumed as simply supported with length $L = 20$ cm. The thickness of each layer was 0.02 cm. The material properties of each lamina were assumed as: $E_1 = 120$ GPa, $E_2 = 7.9$ GPa, $G_{12} = 5.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$ and $\rho = 1.58 \times 10^{-5}$ N-sec²/cm⁴.

Due to symmetry, only a quadrant of the plate was modeled using a 3×3 mesh. A time increment $\Delta t = 10$ μ sec was used. The dynamic responses of the plate under pressure of 0.98 and 4.9 N/cm² are plotted in Fig. 1.

An alternative finite element solution using a 3×3 mesh of 9-node isoparametric quadrilateral elements to model a quadrant of the plate was provided by Chen and Sun [6]. Their results are also plotted in Fig. 1 for comparison and good agreement is observed.

Fig.1- Dynamic responses of a 10-ply $([0^0/90^0/0^0/90^0/0^0]_s)$ Graphite/Epoxy laminated simply supported square plate

Fig.2- Dynamic responses of an orthotropic clamped annular spherical cap

(2) Dynamic Response of an Orthotropic Annular Spherical Cap under Uniform Step Pressure

Dynamic response of an orthotropic annular spherical cap, as shown in Fig. 2, under uniform step pressure were performed. The geometric and material data for the annular spherical cap were assumed as: $H/h = 1.5$, $E_r/E_\theta = 1/3$ and $\nu_\theta = 0.25$.

Since this problem is axisymmetric, a 10-degree segment of the spherical cap was analyzed and six elements were employed. A time increment $\Delta \tau (= [E_\theta/\rho R^2]^{1/2} \Delta t) = 0.01$ was used. The dynamic responses of the spherical cap with $b/a = 0.1$ and 0.5 are plotted in Fig. 2.

An alternative solution to this problem was given by Dumir et al. [7]. In Reference 7, an orthogonal point collocation method in space domain and Newmark scheme in time domain were used to obtain the time response. Their results are also plotted in Fig. 2 for comparison and good agreement is seen.

(3) Buckling of an Orthotropic Axisymmetrically Imperfect Whole Spherical Shell under Uniform Pressure

The static and dynamic buckling analyses for an orthotropic imperfect whole spherical shell, as shown in Fig. 3, under external uniform pressure were performed. The geometric and material data for the whole spherical shell were assumed as: $R/h = 80$, $G_{r\theta}/E_\theta = 0.3684$, and $\nu_r = 0.3$. The imperfections considered were assumed as axisymmetric,

$$w_0(\phi) = -0.25hP_{16}(\cos\phi) \quad (6)$$

where P_{16} is the Legendre polynomial of order 16 and ϕ is the angle between the pole and a point on the meridian of the shell.

For the axisymmetric buckling analysis, a strip of the shell subtending an angle of 10 degrees in the circumferential direction and 90 degrees in the meridional direction was analyzed using six elements. Nine elements were also tried but the results remained the same. For the asymmetric buckling analysis, a 4×6 mesh was used to model an octant of the spherical shell. After substantial numerical experiments, it is found that the maximum time increment $\Delta\tau$ must be less than 0.2 in order to yield converged results. Three cases were considered: (i) static buckling, (ii) undamped dynamic buckling, and (iii) damped dynamic buckling.

Figure 3 shows the results for the undamped and damped dynamic responses of the imperfect whole spherical shell with orthotropic parameter $E_r/E_\theta = 0.25$. The curves for undamped dynamic responses show the interesting phenomenon of dynamic buckling as the uniform step pressure increased by a small amount from $0.51P_{cr}$ to $0.52P_{cr}$, where P_{cr} is defined as,

$$P_{cr} = \frac{2E_r}{[3(1-\nu_r^2)]^{1/2}} \left(\frac{h}{R}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Fig.3- Dynamic responses of an orthotropic imperfect whole spherical shell

Fig.4- Buckling analyses of an imperfect whole spherical shell with various orthotropic properties

The curves for damped dynamic responses show that the viscous damping ($\xi_1 = \xi_2 = 5\%$) has an effect of increasing the dynamic buckling load from $0.515P_{cr}$ to $0.575P_{cr}$, by approximately 12%.

Figure 4 shows the results for nondimensional buckling load (P/P_{cr}) vs. orthotropic parameter (E_r/E_θ) for all three cases. The case of static buckling was analyzed by Tong and Pian [8] previously, and their results were also plotted in Fig. 4 for comparison. Good agreement is shown. It is seen that the dynamic buckling loads are certainly lower than the static buckling loads. The viscous damping has an effect of increasing the dynamic buckling load by about 5 - 15%. It is interesting to see that, for each case, there is a critical value of E_r/E_θ at which the buckling mode changes from axisymmetric to asymmetric. In this example, the critical value of E_r/E_θ is approximately 2 for all three cases.

(4) Buckling of an Orthotropic Asymmetrically Imperfect Spherical Cap under Uniform Step Pressure

The spherical cap considered is shown in Fig. 5. The geometric parameter λ was assumed as 8. The thickness h and radius R were assumed as 0.254 cm and 63.5 cm, respectively. The boundary condition was assumed as clamped. The material properties were assumed as: $E_r = 51.75$ GPa, $E_\theta = 207$ GPa, $E_r/E_\theta = 0.25$, $G_{r\theta} = 7.757$ GPa, and $\nu_\theta = 1/3$. The imperfection was assumed as asymmetric, which was confined within the shape of a cut pie, as shown in the shaded zone in Fig. 5. The imperfection was defined as

$$w_0(\phi, \theta) = -64\delta h \left(\frac{25}{7} \sin\phi \right)^3 \left(1 - \frac{25}{7} \sin\phi \right)^3 \cos 2\theta \quad (8)$$

The imperfection zone was assumed to be confined within a quadrant of the spherical cap, i.e., $|\theta| \leq 45$ degrees. Due to symmetry, only half of the shell need be analyzed and 20 elements were used, as shown in Fig. 5, among which eight were used to model the imperfect zone. The nondimensional time increment was chosen as $\Delta\tau = 0.25$.

Fig.5- Undamped dynamic responses of an orthotropic clamped spherical cap

Fig.6- Damped dynamic responses of an orthotropic clamped spherical cap.

Figure 5 shows the results for the undamped dynamic responses of the spherical cap with $\delta = 0.0$ and 0.4 . The curves for the perfect shell ($\delta = 0.0$) show the interesting phenomenon of dynamic buckling as the uniform step pressure increased by a small amount from $0.74P_{cr}$ to $0.75P_{cr}$. The curves for the imperfect shell ($\delta = 0.4$) show that the dynamic buckling load is reduced to between $0.69P_{cr}$ and $0.70P_{cr}$. The effect of amplitude of imperfection on dynamic buckling load is apparent.

Figure 6 shows the results for the damped dynamic responses of the spherical cap with $\delta = 0.0$ and 0.4 . The curves for the perfect shell ($\delta = 0.0$) show the obvious dynamic buckling effect when the uniform step pressure is slightly increased from $0.79P_{cr}$ to $0.80P_{cr}$. The curves for the imperfect shell ($\delta = 0.4$) show that the dynamic buckling load is reduced to between $0.73P_{cr}$ and $0.74P_{cr}$. Again, the effect of amplitude of imperfection on damped dynamic buckling load is apparent. When comparing the results shown in Figs. 5 and 6, it is observed that the assumed viscous damping based on two fundamental modal damping ratios of 5% has the effect of increasing the dynamic buckling load by approximately 5%.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, the dynamic buckling behavior of a variety of orthotropic and anisotropic, imperfect, thin shells are studied. Good agreements are seen between some fundamental results and available solutions. New results were also obtained to quantify the effect of amplitude of imperfections, which can significantly reduce the buckling load. The results also quantify the effects of polarly orthotropic material parameter (E_r/E_θ) and viscous damping.

The present finite element method may provide a tool for the analysis of the dynamic response and buckling of imperfect laminated thin shell structures. The present numerical results and the interpretations of physical phenomena for the various cases of shells with various ranges of parameters should provide some insight and convenience to the analysts as well as designers of thin shell structures.

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